

Optimization of Bidirectional Modular DC/DC Converter for Low and High Power Operation in Aircraft Applications

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Abstract — This paper presents a multi-objective optimization method for DC/DC converters used in More Electrical Aircrafts applications. Very high efficiency associated with high power density requires the use of wide bandgap devices, such as SiC semiconductors. Results show that, due to the use of SiC devices, the designed converter produces lower losses at hard-switching (HS) modulation than at soft-switching (SS) modulation. Furthermore, we show that there is an optimal number of small converters in parallel, which provides high efficiency even at low power as well as high reliability, compared to a single converter.

Index Terms — Aircraft, DC/DC converter, modular converter, SiC semiconductors, converter optimization.

I. INTRODUCTION

One of the main challenges nowadays is to develop more ecological solutions in order to reduce the human impact in the environment and make it more sustainable [1]. For this reason, the aircraft industry has largely invested in More Electrical Aircrafts (MEA), which may, at the same time, reduce aircraft weight and fuel consumption. For that, it is crucial to design power converters with the most effective solutions in terms of energy efficiency, power density, reliability and costs, which is the purpose of this work.

New aircraft generation is supposed to replace traditional pneumatic and hydraulic systems by electrical actuators and machines [2]. In this context, several power converters are employed in order to provide energy from a main source to such mechanisms.

In certain MEA applications, a bidirectional power converter is required to control the voltage, current and power between the aircraft electrical network and a storage element. Storage systems must be able to deliver a large amount of energy in a short period of time (high power), but usually they are slowly charged (low power). Thus, since the delivered energy by the battery and its charging energy are the same in a flight cycle, a power converter between battery and electrical network must have high efficiency both at high and low power.

This paper proposes a methodology for the precise optimization of DC/DC power converters. The system

considered is composed by an aircraft DC network with $\pm 270\text{Vdc}$ nominal voltage and an ion-lithium battery set with 570Vdc nominal voltage. The network differential voltage can oscillate between 500Vdc and 650Vdc in normal mode operation, reaching transiently 900V in case of failure. Battery voltage vary from 300V to 650V , depending on its charge level. Nominal power is 40kW in source mode and 5kW in charging mode. In addition, other requirements and standards should be satisfied:

- Global converter efficiency greater than 99% at high and low power (source and charging mode);
- Total converter weight (power stage) lower than 10kg;
- Airbus HVDC Power Quality Standard (0 – 150kHz);
- Conducted Emissions DO-160 Standard (150kHz – 152MHz) - Category L.

Considering these specifications, this converter requires the state of the art in semiconductors technology, once that high switching frequencies are needed to reduce passive weights, increasing power density and, at the same time, semiconductor losses must be kept in low levels. Wide band-gap semiconductors (silicon carbide - SiC and gallium nitrite - GaN) need to be considered in this kind of application. Due to the voltage level of this converter, only SiC-based devices were explored, as will be discussed in Section II.

Furthermore, soft-switching techniques will be presented and compared to hard-switching ones. It will be shown that, contrarily to silicon-based (Si) devices, soft-switching not only increases switching losses in SiC semiconductors compared to hard-switching, but it also increases conduction losses and system complexity.

This work also proposes a scheme based on modularity of converters. Even using high performance semiconductors, efficiency at high and low power is only achieved with lower power converters in parallel, as will be shown in Section II. This section presents also the optimization approach and provides a more complete analysis about converter topology, including the model and optimization of heat sinks, given semiconductor losses. Passives and filters will be discussed in Section III.

Finally, the results with the proposed system are summarized in Section IV, followed by the conclusion.

II. GLOBAL OPTIMIZATION APPROACH

An overview of the multi-objective optimization methodology is illustrated in Fig. 1. The purpose is to analyse the impact of three input variables in the system: 1) switching frequency (F_{sw}); 2) main inductor current ripple (I_{ripL}), calculated as a percentage of the inductor mean current; 3) number of modular converters operating in parallel (N).

The set of input parameters are varied in order to specify a minimum converter associated with the set (F_{sw}, I_{ripL}, N). For this application, losses and weight are the optimization targets. Then, each solution is placed in a *Pareto Front*, which determines an optimal curve as a function of the objectives.

Considering that it is a multi-objective system (*Efficiency vs. Weight*), the best converter is chosen based on application criteria and engineer's decisions. For aircraft applications, it is usually required the converter with maximum power density, but with an efficiency above the minimum specified.

Since the number of solutions is equal to the number of input combinations, it is recommended to choose reasonable restrictions for the input values, defined in a preselection, to reduce unnecessary computational efforts.

A. Modular Converters

The design of multiple converters in parallel presents some advantages when compared to a single module with total power, even though it may not be the most compact solution. As stated before, presenting high efficiency at low power is important when the converter is operating in charging mode. This is particularly difficult to achieve with a single converter supposed to work at high and low power. At high power, the converter requires power semiconductor with low on-state resistance ($R_{DS(on)}$). However, low $R_{DS(on)}$ implies in components with high parasitic capacitances, which present high switching losses. These switching losses result in low efficiency at low power operation point.

Fig. 2 shows some efficiency profiles as a function of the output power, considering a modular converter with nominal power 40kW, divided in six 6.7kW modules in parallel. The variable N_{on} is the number of enabled modules, which can vary from one to six. The black curve also in Fig. 2 is the overall efficiency profile if N_{on} is controlled as a function of the output power. Thus, high efficiency even at low power is achieved.

Using parallel modules may also improve the system reliability, allowing degraded operation by turning-off modules in damage. Another advantage is that redundancy can be provided with lower cost, since one or more spare modules can be added into the converter. Finally, parallelization also allows interleaving modules, which optimize output capacitors, as discussed in [3].

In terms of optimization, the number of modules in parallel N will be assumed as a variable in the model. This variable was introduced considering that: 1) for a given discrete semiconductor, a converter module is designed to have the maximum power with only one device per position S_1, S_2, S_3 and S_4 (i.e., without semiconductors in parallel), according to the efficiency and density power specifications; 2) N is the number of similar modules required to achieve nominal power.

Fig. 1. Illustration of the proposed optimization methodology.

Fig. 2. Efficiency profile of modular converters in parallel. The variable N_{on} refers to the number of enabled converters operating in parallel in a system.

B. Converter Topology

Many bidirectional DC/DC topologies have been considered for similar applications [4], [5], including multi-level ones [6]. An advantage of series multilevel converters is that it allows the use of lower voltage semiconductors, such as GaN HEMTs, even for medium or high voltage converters, avoiding direct series association. Nevertheless, multilevel converters increase the number of devices, without redundancy improvement, which is not recommended in applications requiring high level of reliability.

The Bidirectional Buck + Boost Cascade is shown in the Fig. 3. Reference [4] proposes a soft-switching (SS) strategy to achieve lower switching losses in Si MOSFETs compared to ordinary hard-switching (HS) one. This topology was considered in the present work given its high flexibility when dealing with high voltage variation in both sides. It is also bidirectional and can be used in hard or soft-switching modes for performance optimization.

1) Soft-switching versus Hard-switching

The differences between HS and SS modulation techniques are exemplified in the inductor's current waveforms, shown in Figs. 4(a) and 4(b). The curves consider a given operation point, when power flows from battery to network, and network voltage (V_{net}) are higher than battery voltage (V_{bat}).

Fig. 3. Complete single module of the Bidirectional Buck + Boost Cascade, including filters.

Fig. 4. (a) Inductor current in hard-switching mode; (b) Inductor current in soft-switching mode.

In HS mode, only one leg commutates. Considering the current sense in the circuit, S_2 will be turned-on and turned-off at high voltage and high current, whereas S_1 will always commute at zero voltage due to its antiparallel diode. Since the second leg (formed by S_3 and S_4) is not switching, only conduction losses are expected in S_3 (S_4 is off).

In Si MOSFET devices, turn-on losses are quite higher than turn-off ones. For this reason, SS mode ensures zero voltage switching (ZVS) in turn-on commutations, in order to avoid its losses. However, both legs need to commute to reverse the sense of the current, and all the switches need to turn-off at high voltage and high current. In summary, HS presents two commutations at high voltage and high current in one switching cycle: a single turn-on and a single turn-off. In contrast, SS has four turn-off commutations at high voltage and high current, but all the turn-on commutations are executed in ZVS.

Differently from Si switches, this trade-off between the number of commutations and the type of commutation (turn-on or turn-off) are not advantageous for SiC devices, since the difference between turn-on and turn-off losses is not so high. Table I shows the switching losses calculated from the Figs. 4(a) and 4(b) waveforms, taking as an example the discrete SiC MOSFET *C3M0016120K* and a switching frequency of 40kHz. In this case, SS presents higher switching losses than HS for the same conditions.

Furthermore, in SS mode the inductor current ripple needs to be higher than in HS, in order to reverse the sense of the current and allow turn-on at zero voltage. This causes a higher rms current and, consequently, higher conduction losses. Conduction losses obtained from the same waveforms are also shown in Table I.

In both modulation methods, inductor L is shared by the two

TABLE I. COMPARISON OF LOSSES BETWEEN HS AND SS MODES

	HS Mode	SS Mode
Turn-on Losses	10.2W	0.0W
Turn-off Losses	2.1W	12.9W
Total Sw. Losses	12.3W	12.9W
Rms Current	20.0A	27.4A
Conduction Losses	22.0W	41.4W
Total SiC Losses	45.3W	54.3W

legs and it is designed for the worst case in terms of rms current, maximum current and ripple current. Higher current ripple reduces inductance, but increases maximum current and rms current. As described by [4], inductor size is theoretically assumed proportional to its stored energy, which is proportional to the ratio between power and switching frequency. It means that, in a first step, the choice between HS or SS does not affect inductor volume and weight. However, with HS modulation, it is possible to choose an arbitrary inductor ripple, in order to verify the impact of this variable in a real design.

Finally, a considerable control effort and a suitable hardware to detect zero voltage are necessary to implement SS mode. For all these reasons, soft-switching will be not used in the optimization model.

C. Semiconductors Model

Semiconductors must be initially chosen regarding the maximum voltage and power requirements, in order to select a proper technology. Since this topology is two-level, each switch must withstand the full input/output voltage range.

Concerning the information about maximum input voltage specified for this converter (up to 900V), silicon-based MOSFETs or GaN HEMTs cannot be used, since their maximum voltages are lower or close to the voltage specification limit. Moreover, an order of tens of kilohertz is supposed to be necessary to cope with weight and efficiency requirements, which is not usually possible with IGBTs. That is the reason why only SiC MOSFETs were evaluated here.

A general approach for the semiconductors model is discussed in [7]. The scheme is based on datasheet curves, which provide information about conduction and switching characteristics as a function of the voltage and the current applied into devices. A circuit simulation or calculation tool can be easily used to estimate losses in one switching period and, consequently, the power dissipated by the semiconductors. Simulations must consider full power and the worst case in terms of voltage and current levels, giving the highest losses.

From information about packaging thermal resistances and maximum junction power, a thermal circuit is calculated with the purpose of estimating the needed heat sink thermal resistance

and the thermal interface material. Usually, discrete semiconductor weight is negligible when compared to heat sink weight. Thus, it is necessary to find the lighter thermal solution, composed by a heat sink and a fan, to achieve a required thermal resistance, as discussed in the next topic.

D. Heat Sink Model

Although heat sinks can be accurately modelled with finite elements methods (FEM), a long time is required for each simulation [9]. Methods based on thermal resistance measurements are not quite useful in optimization, since it is only applied for a specific set heat sink-fan.

The method used in this paper was developed in [8], which provides a forced-air cooling analytical model based on fluid mechanics and heat transfer equations. This model estimates the power components mean temperature (or heat sink thermal resistance if a set of components are symmetrically located in the heat sink), given the heat sink dimensions and fan curves. For a set of parameters such as width, length, height, number of fins, thickness of fins, and others, it is possible to create a curve *thermal resistance R_{th} vs. weight* with best heat sinks for a specific fan.

Fig. 5 shows a heat sink profile and the switches configuration, considering one modular converter. A minimum area is required to assemble the switches, which defines the minimum values of width and length. The input parameters defined are described in Table II.

The overall solutions were calculated for all the input dimensions. Results are present in the “ *R_{th} vs. weight*” graph, shown in Fig. 6. The best curve (in red) is obtained by selecting the lightest heat sink for a specific R_{th} .

III. PASSIVE COMPONENTS SELECTION

It is well known that increasing the converter switching frequency is important to reduce the size of passive components, but it increases switching losses and, consequently, heat sink weight. For that reason, an optimal switching frequency can be found in order to provide the lowest weight for the system.

An approach discussed in [1] uses a database with numerous devices from the market. At first, passive quantities are calculated considering design specifications, such as current and voltage ripple, frequency cut-off, EMI standards, etc. Similarly, the maximum electrical quantities in which they are submitted need to be obtained (maximum voltage, maximum current, etc). All this information is used in order to determine a space of possible devices and combinations. The next subsections will discuss more about passives individually.

A. Main Inductor

The main inductor was shown in Fig. 3. The inductance can be easily calculated for each input set (F_{sw} , I_{ripL} , N), based on its terminal voltage profile in one switching cycle and the desired current ripple, using:

$$L = \frac{\Delta V_L^2}{F_{SW} \cdot (P/N) \cdot I_{ripL}} \cdot \frac{V_{bater}}{V_{netcr}} \quad (1)$$

where V_{bater} and V_{netcr} are the battery and network critical voltages, respectively, for the worst case in terms of current ripple in the inductor, ΔV_L is the maximum voltage drop between inductor terminals and P the nominal power.

TABLE II. INPUT PARAMETERS FOR HEAT SINK OPTIMIZATION

Parameter	Min.	Step	Max.
Width (mm)	25	5	120
Length (mm)	80	5	150
Baseplate thick. (mm)	3	1	10
Fins height (mm)	10	2.5	120
Fins thickness (mm)	1	0.25	3
Number of fins	5	1	40
Fans	Ebm-papst (614 NHH-119, 414J, 424JM, 424J); Sanyo Denki (9GA0424P3M001); Sunon (MF30100V1, MF30150V1, MF25060V1)		

Fig. 5. Semiconductors assembly on the heat sink and heat sink profile with the dimension definitions.

Fig. 6. Heat sink optimization. Overall heat sinks are calculated by the analytical model. The curve with best heat sinks is determined.

For a given nominal power and voltage range, the inductor size is most impacted by its current ripple and converter switching frequency. The worst case must be tracked considering overall voltage range and both operation modes (Buck and Boost). For this project, maximum ripple current occurs when the duty cycle is 0.5 and for $V_{bat} = 325V$ and $V_{net} = 650V$ at maximum power.

However, inductor design is not straightforward. It must consider maximum peak current to avoid core saturation, and magnetic losses need to be estimated in order to respect thermal constraints. Based on the inductor model, detailed in [10], an algorithm was implemented with the purpose of designing different inductors from a core database with maximum losses and maximum temperature constraints. Then, the lightest option is selected.

B. Battery Side Capacitor

Capacitors connected in parallel with switching legs have capacitance values determined to ensure a specified maximum voltage ripple and comply with EMI standards, that defines maximum current and voltage spectra.

The battery side capacitor is defined by the voltage ripple constraint and by its current. It can be obtained using:

$$C_{bat} = \frac{\int_0^T i_{C_{bat}} dt}{\Delta V_{bat}} \quad (2)$$

where ΔV_{bat} is the maximum voltage ripple and $i_{C_{bat}}$ is the battery

side capacitor current, obtained analytically or by simulation and integrated in one switching period. A numerical integration can be directly made by using a capacitor current time vector calculated by simulations, and must consider the worst case in terms of charge transfer to the capacitor.

Finally, an algorithm is implemented in order to take capacitors from a DC link capacitors database and select the best devices, including parallel and series association of these capacitors. Maximum quantities such as the voltage and current ripple at the switching frequency are taken into account. Differently from inductors, capacitor's datasheets usually provide all the required information.

C. Differential-mode filters

The design of the differential-mode filter depends on some constraints: 1) Current harmonics injected into the network at the worst operation point must be below the limits imposed by aircraft manufacturers; 2) Harmonics absorbed by the network must not produce voltage harmonics in the converter input greater than defined by standards, for stability reasons [12].

The calculation of the required C_i , L_i and C_{net} is complex, since the switching converter is a nonlinear system and an analytical expression is difficult to achieve. Thus, an optimization model is developed with the purpose of selecting appropriate values to comply with required standards and, at the same time, find the combination with the lowest weight. In this first design, interleaved converters approach was not considered.

In some conditions, damping circuits must be used with the purpose of reducing resonance peaks from LC filters and guaranteeing low output impedance even close to its cut-off frequencies [11], [12]. Nevertheless, it generates power losses, reducing efficiency and increasing weight. Instead, the differential-mode filter is calculated in order to keep resonance points below one-tenth of the switching frequency. In this way, the control system can have enough bandwidth to control the voltage in C_i , and supply low frequency currents required by the loads [13]. With this approach, the closed-loop system's impedance seen by the network will comply with stability requirements.

D. Common-mode filters

The presence of high dV/dt caused by fast switching of SiC devices generates high common-mode currents [14]. Precise common-mode circuit models are difficult to be developed, especially because the majority of parasitic elements are distributed along physical dimensions. Some works provide models based on rough approximations or experimental analysis. Nevertheless, by adopting a conservative approach, it is possible to have at least a first filter estimation, which can be adjusted to obtain the required performance.

A common-mode circuit model was obtained as presented in [15] and adapted for DC/DC converters. Inductances L_{CMi} and L_{CMout} , as well as the capacitances C_{CMi} and C_{CMout} shown in Fig. 3, were found iteratively by comparing the currents calculated by the model with limits provided by EMI standards. Circuit parameters external to the converter are estimated by measurements in a real plant, or using FEM [15]. The inner parasitic elements can be estimated using a fixed mechanical structure, which is usually unfeasible in initial stages of the converter design. In this case, capacitances provided by device datasheets can be used as dominant parameters.

IV. CALCULATION RESULTS

A. Optimal Design

Calculations were made for the definitions summarized in Table III. All converter solutions were obtained according to the approach proposed and are presented in the Fig. 7. The Pareto Front is traced taking the best solutions to fulfil the objectives: maximum efficiency at nominal power and maximum power density, simultaneously.

The criterion used to select the best converter was consider the lighter option that satisfies the efficiency requirement. The optimal modular converter is also indicated in Fig. 7 and has the following parameters: $F_{sw} = 50\text{kHz}$; $I_{ripL} = 60\%$; $N = 8$ (8 modular converters in parallel). The calculated weight is 6.1kg and its efficiency is 99.0% at nominal power.

It is important to mention that the maximum efficiency of the total converter at nominal power (40kW) is the same efficiency for each of the eight modules at 5kW. This means that, since the maximum power required is exactly 5kW in charging mode, the converter also achieves high efficiency at low power, as defined for this application. By using a single converter with eight SiC MOSFETs in parallel, with same F_{sw} and I_{ripL} , the calculated maximum efficiency at 5kW is 97.1%.

The weight and loss distributions for the sum of the eight converters in parallel are shown in Figs. 8(a) and 8(b). It is important to note that the main inductor has the highest impact in the converter weight, followed by the differential-mode filters. The heat sink represents lower than 10% of the total weight, which can be explained by the high efficiency specification. This means that low losses are expected in the overall converter and a small cooling solution is required.

B. Efficiency vs. Power Density

Figs. 9(a) and 9(b) shows some curves that clarify the relevance of the inductor current ripple choice. For the same number of converters in parallel (six), its efficiency and power density are plotted for different switching frequencies and inductor current ripples. The optimal results have the current ripple between 40% and 60% of the inductor mean current.

Despite not shown, the inductor current ripple almost only influences the main inductor in the converter. To achieve low current ripple, the inductance needs to be higher for the same current level, forcing the inductor core to be larger to fit a higher number of turns. In contrast, for a high current ripple, the losses are more relevant due to core hysteresis, and the peak current is higher for a given rms current. In this case, larger core is also necessary.

Finally, all the specific results depends on the developed models and the databases considered. Since this paper deal with a discrete optimization, a slight change in some parameters can produce a different optimal converter. It is convenient to be conservative, analyse more than one solution and make a decision taken into account some margin.

TABLE III. REQUIREMENTS AND INPUT PARAMETERS RANGE

Switching frequency	20kHz to 100kHz
Inductor current ripple	10% to 100%
Number of converters in parallel	4 to 12
Discrete semiconductor	SiC MOSFET C3M0016120K
Minimum efficiency	99%
Minimum power density	4kW/kg (max. 10kg)

Fig. 7. Pareto Front with the optimal converter obtained.

Fig. 8.(a) Weight and (b) losses distribution of the optimal converter.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This paper proposed an optimization method for DC/DC converters, in which the whole system was considered in order to achieve high efficiency and power density. The bidirectional cascade Buck + Boost topology was chosen due to its features relative to the specification. In the context of More Electrical Aircrafts (MEA), high efficiency at low power and high reliability are also required. For this reason, an approach based in modular converters was discussed.

It was shown in the results that passive components has an important impact on converter weight. The use of SiC-based semiconductors lead to solutions with better power density, since it allows the increase of the switching frequency. Furthermore, in contrast to silicon-based devices, soft-switching (SS) techniques may not result in lower losses in wide bandgap semiconductors, once that it increases the number of commutations and the rms current.

The model of each part of the converter was introduced with the aim of giving some orientation for a complete design. The Pareto Front with all solutions, as well as the optimal converter, were presented, followed by interesting results about the impact of each variable in the system. The accuracy of the results depends on the validation of each model. In a first approach, based only on datasheet information, this method is quite useful to guide an initial design by comparing different topologies, devices and technologies, and providing an idea about volume, weight and costs necessary to meet the requirements.

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Fig. 9. Impact of inductor current ripple in the converter for (a) 10% to 40% and (b) 40% to 100% for 6 modules in parallel.

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